

**ИДЕИ ТОЛЕРАНТНОСТИ В ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЯХ
АЛИШЕРА НАВОИ**

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Аннотация.

В статье исследуются идеи толерантности в духовном наследии Алишера Навои — выдающегося поэта и философа эпохи Тимуридов. Анализируются историко-культурные предпосылки формирования взглядов Навои на межрелигиозное и межэтническое взаимодействие, раскрывается философское понимание им толерантности как духовного и социального феномена. Особое внимание уделяется гуманистическим аспектам его творчества, проявляющимся в уважении к представителям различных вероисповеданий и народов. Автор подчеркивает актуальность идей Навои в контексте современных вызовов, связанных с многообразием культур и религий.

Ключевые слова:

Алишер Навои, толерантность, духовное наследие, межрелигиозный диалог, межэтническое взаимодействие, гуманизм, философия ислама, мультикультурализм, гуманистические идеи, Тимуриды.

Annotation: The article examines the ideas of tolerance in the spiritual heritage of Alisher Navoi, an outstanding poet and philosopher of the Timurid era. It analyzes the historical and cultural prerequisites for the formation of Navoi's views on interreligious and interethnic interaction, and reveals his philosophical

understanding of tolerance as a spiritual and social phenomenon. Particular attention is paid to the humanistic aspects of his work, manifested in respect for representatives of various faiths and peoples. The author emphasizes the relevance of Navoi's ideas in the context of modern challenges associated with the diversity of cultures and religions.

Key words: Alisher Navoi, tolerance, spiritual heritage, interreligious dialogue, interethnic interaction, humanism, philosophy of Islam, multiculturalism, humanistic ideas, Timurids.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada temuriylar davrining atoqli shoiri va faylasufi Alisher Navoiyning ma'naviy merosidagi bag'rikenglik g'oyalari ko'rib chiqiladi. Navoiyning dinlararo va millatlararo o'zaro munosabatlarga oid qarashlari shakllanishining tarixiy-madaniy shart-sharoitlari tahlil qilinib, bag'rikenglikni ma'naviy-ijtimoiy hodisa sifatida falsafiy tushunishi ochib berilgan. Uning ijodida turli din va elat vakillariga hurmat-ehtiromda namoyon bo'lgan insonparvarlik jihatlariga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan. Muallif madaniyatlar va dinlar xilma-xilligi bilan bog'liq zamonaviy muammolar kontekstida Navoiy g'oyalarining dolzarbligini ta'kidlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: Alisher Navoiy, bag'rikenglik, ma'naviy meros, dinlararo muloqot, millatlararo o'zaro munosabatlar, insonparvarlik, islom falsafasi, multikulturalizm, insonparvarlik g'oyalari, temuriylar.

Introduction

Alisher Navoi is one of the greatest thinkers and poets of the East, whose philosophical legacy remains relevant today. His works clearly express the ideas of humanism and tolerance, which he considered the basis of a just and prosperous society.

Navoi emphasized the importance of respect for human dignity, equality of peoples and cultures, and the need for moral improvement of the individual. The

issues of humanism and tolerance in his works are reflected in the context of Islamic ethics, Sufi philosophy, and the socio-political thought of that time.

The purpose of this article is to reveal the concept of an ideal society in the works of Alisher Navoi, to identify the main principles of his humanism and tolerance, and to show their significance for the modern world.

The Timurid era was a time of intense cultural exchange and coexistence of various ethnic and religious groups: Muslims (Sunnis and Shiites), Christians, Jews, Zoroastrians and others. In this diversity, ideas of mutual understanding and tolerance became an important factor in social stability.

Alisher Navoi, being a Sunni Muslim, showed deep respect for all faiths and peoples, which is reflected in his works both in direct statements and in artistic images. His philosophical views were based on Islam, but were distinguished by their breadth and humanism, going beyond the narrow confessional approach.

Literature review

The study of the idea of tolerance in the works of Eastern thinkers is based on the analysis of classical philosophical and religious texts, as well as modern interpretations of these concepts.

In the comparative context of tolerance, a significant role was played by Abu Reyhan Beruni, who studied the interaction of various cultures and religions. Alisher Navoi developed humanistic ideas, calling for peaceful coexistence of peoples, and Yusuf Khos Khozib in his work "Kutadgu Bilig" described the ethical standards of the ruler and the need to respect representatives of various social groups. Saadi Shirazi emphasized the philosophy of compassion and mercy in his works, considering them as fundamental foundations of peaceful coexistence. The Sufi poet Hafiz also contributed to the development of ideas of spiritual unification of humanity through poetry.

Research Methodology

This study used such methods and means of scientific knowledge as analysis

and synthesis, complex and systemic analysis, comparison of conceptual theories.

Analysis and results of the study

In Navoi's work, the idea of tolerance is linked to the concept of justice and spiritual equality of all people. He repeatedly emphasized that true faith requires love and respect for all humanity, regardless of religious differences.

In the poem "Haft Divan" Navoi writes about the need for mutual respect and acceptance of others, indicating that differences are part of the divine plan. The poet believes that there is no superiority of one nation or faith over another, for all people are equal before God.

In one of his philosophical treatises, Navoi asserts: "God created people different so that they could get to know each other and learn patience and love, and not for the sake of enmity and hatred" [1, p. 124].

Thus, tolerance in Navoi's understanding is not just a passive acceptance of others, but an active striving for spiritual understanding and unity.

Navoi showed a respect for other religions that was rare for his time. His works contain dialogues and images in which representatives of different faiths engage in cultural and philosophical exchanges.

Thus, in the poem "Leyli and Majnun" he shows that love and spiritual values surpass religious differences. The image of Leyli and Majnun symbolizes universal human feelings and aspirations that do not depend on confession.

In addition, in his treatises, Navoi spoke out against fanaticism and religious intolerance, considering them an obstacle to the harmonious development of society: "Fanaticism is a poison that destroys people's hearts and gives rise to evil" [2, p. 98].

Navoi believed that true religiosity manifests itself in mercy, justice, and love for everyone without exception. For Navoi, the idea of tolerance was also important as a social principle. He understood that the diversity of the population requires a wise and fair attitude from rulers and society as a whole.

In his works, Navoi calls for social solidarity and cooperation of all classes, this is the key to the prosperity of the people and well-being in the country, which can only be ensured by a wise and fair ruler. Navoi sees the main quality of a ruler in the presence of spiritual and moral virtues and intellect. The thinker sees justice as the main measure in governing the country. His state ideal is high moral traits - wisdom, humanism, truthfulness: "People have many good signs and distinctions, but there is no distinction better than justice. Without it, there is nothing human, without righteous qualities, there is nothing except misfortunes" [3,344c.p.246]

In his letters and messages, Navoi appealed to the rulers to respect the rights of all citizens, regardless of their origin and faith, emphasizing that only in an atmosphere of tolerance is sustainable peace and prosperity possible.

Navoi called on rulers to be wise and fair, to protect the poor and weak, and to promote the development of science and culture. In his works, one can find a justification for the social responsibility of power and the importance of moral improvement of society's leaders. He emphasized that without the spiritual development of the ruler, it is impossible to build a fair society. His work "Saddi Iskandari" (Iskander's Wall) reflects the ideas of fair governance based on the principles of goodness, wisdom and care for people.

According to Navoi, it is through understanding and accepting differences that a fair and harmonious society can be built, which makes his views relevant in the modern era of globalization and intercultural conflicts.

Conclusions

The ideas of tolerance in the spiritual heritage of Alisher Navoi represent an important contribution to the world philosophical and cultural tradition. His humanistic approach to interreligious and interethnic dialogue, emphasis on love and respect for others are a striking example, relevant both for his time and for the present.

In the context of modern challenges associated with conflicts on religious and

ethnic grounds, Navoi's legacy serves as a powerful source of inspiration and a reminder of the value of tolerance and mutual understanding.

Navoi highly valued the role of education and adherence to moral standards in human relationships, in the spiritual development of the individual, glorified in his works loyalty to the cause of the state and the people, friendship, brotherhood, truthfulness and integrity, devotion to science and education, and with the power of his talent embodied all the best.

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